

Supplementary Table S1. Doubling time of BY4741 strain under ethanol stress after tunicamycin pre-exposure.

Pre-exposure to tunicamycin ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	Condition after pre-exposure (v/v)	Doubling time (hours)
0	0% Ethanol	1.95 ± 0.12
0.1	0% Ethanol	1.97 ± 0.10
0.2	0% Ethanol	2.06 ± 0.04
0	6% Ethanol	2.85 ± 0.04
0.1	6% Ethanol	2.78 ± 0.11
0.2	6% Ethanol	$2.65 \pm 0.09^*$
0	8% Ethanol	3.21 ± 0.14
0.1	8% Ethanol	3.33 ± 0.24
0.2	8% Ethanol	$2.74 \pm 0.02^*$
0	10% Ethanol	4.19 ± 0.21
0.1	10% Ethanol	4.12 ± 0.22
0.2	10% Ethanol	$3.73 \pm 0.14^*$

* A Dunnett's test for multiple comparisons was used in order to obtain significant differences among pre-exposed cells and its corresponding control. Values represent the mean of five biological replicates.